

STRUCTURAL DESCRIPTION OF TOURISTIC TERMS IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

Farokhat Yunusova

Uzbekistan State World Languages university, 2nd year master
student on the branch of Linguistics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6570103>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st May 2022

Accepted: 10th May 2022

Online: 17th May 2022

KEY WORDS

*tourism, terms, concept,
terminology, term-
creation, equivalent,
classification.*

ABSTRACT

Currently, the field of tourism is also developing rapidly, and the education system has begun to train specialists in new areas of tourism. All this requires the development of an accelerated terminology system in the field of tourism as users of this terms are increasing year by year.

Introduction

The field of terminology plays an important role in the development of linguistics. This article mainly focuses on terms related to tourism, their structure and meanings in Uzbek language. In the 30s of XX century many Uzbek terminological dictionaries were compiled and published. At the same point, theoretical issues about history of terms, the meaning and subject of the terms groups grammatical structure and formation of terms, way of development and source of enrichment. Though terminological system has not yet been studied theoretically, tourism terminology has a special place in Uzbek terminology. The development of Uzbek touristic terms in its early stages, whereas the base of lexicons are multiplying according to the proliferation of the

tourism sphere in the country. If we consider the fact of English to be in the highest status in term-creation of Tourism terminology, it is natural for Uzbek to borrow terms and terminological groups from English. In last century, terms relating to various fields borrowed by European language via Russian, today they came to Uzbek directly. Obviously, there are terms elements in international terms concerning Greek and Latin. It can also considered as a scientific issues to check terms elements in touristic terms.

Main body

Structurally, simple, complex and composite terms might be observed in Uzbek. According to genetic feature, simple terms divided into two groups:

- Simple pre-existing touristic terms in Uzbek;

- Simple touristic terms which is directed borrowed from international languages.

1. Terms that are actively used in the field of tourism which was created based on the internal capabilities of Uzbek, like bayram, bo'xona, buyurtma, mablag', marosim, mijoz, mozor, mehmonxona, qala, qo'riqxonalar, qabulxonalar, mehmonxonalar, safar, qayiq, sayr, sayrgoh, shikoyat, sihatgoh, ta'minot, tashrif, xona, yo'llanma, yo'lovchi, yodgorlik, yotoqxonalar, ziyorat, ziyoratgoh, joylashtirish, bandlash, mo'ljallash

Due to the inner possibilities and morphological peculiarities of each language in term formation, some affixes are claimed productive. In contrast to English and Russian, there are not dominant suffixes to create exactly touristic terms in Uzbek. Complex terms without affixes in structure are not found as terms in pure touristic character, cause such terms are used in both social life and scientific terminology. For example, the term customs in economics, reserve in the field of ecology, monument, shrine can be used as active terms in history.

2. The most effective method of borrowing words in modern stage of language development is calque. It is the way of conveyance the conception with existent units which is non-existent in a language. When the problem of word acquisition analyzed it is found that direct word acquisition from other languages is active in Uzbek.

Terms which are directly borrowed from other foreign languages can be mastered to native language with no changes in structure and meaning and partial phonetic modifications. The following terms can be engaged to such type:

Apartament – sharoiti jihatdan zamonaviy turarjoyga yaqin holda tashkil qilingan, ovqat tayyorlash imkoniyati ham mavjud bo'lgan xona. Bu termin ifodalagan ma'noning muhim jihati xona ichida mijozning o'zi ovqat tayyorlashi mumkinligidir. Odatda, mehmonxonalarda bunday turdagi xonalar bo'lmaydi. Demak, bu terminning paydo bo'lishi uchun lug'aviy asos mehmonxonada tashkil etilgan yangi turdagi xona nomi bilan bog'liqdir.

Gid – turistlarga shaharning yoki ma'lum diqqatga sazovor joylarini ko'rsatuvchi, bir yoki bir nechta tillarni biluvchi professional yo'l boshlovchi. Bu termin iste'molda faol qo'llanadi.

Tabldot – restoranlarda taomga nisbatan qo'llanuvchi, gazakdan tortib desert miqdorigacha chegaralangan va ovqatlarga umumiy narxlar o'rnatilgan xizmat ko'rsatish turi. Odatda esa har bir taomga alohida belgilangan narxlar asosida xizmat ko'rsatiladi.

Taymsher – alohida yoki birgalikdagi kvartira tipidagi, uzoq muddatga sotib olish mumkin bo'lgan xona.

Tranzit – bir hududdan ikkinchi hududga uchinchi hudud orqali 24 soatdan ko'p bo'lmagan vaqtda yo'lovchi, yuk kabilarni olib o'tish. Bu termin tranzit yuk, tranzit yo'lovchi kabi birikma shaklidagi boshqa terminlarni hosil qilishda ham qatnashadi.

Transfer – turistik markazning ichkarisida turistni istalgan joyga tashish (vokzal, aeroport, dengiz portidan mehmonxonaga yoki shu yo'nalishning qaramaqarshisi; bir vokzal, aeroport, dengiz portidan boshqasiga; mehmonxonadan teatrga yoki qarama-qarshi yo'nalishda tashish).

Charter – transport vositasi xo'jayini bilan ijaraga oluvchi o'rtasida ushbu transport

vositasidan ma'lum muddat yoki reysga foydalanib turish haqida tuzilgan ijara shartnomasi.

Lyuks - mehmonxonadagi nomerlar kategoriyasi bo'lib, mijozga taqdim etilayotgan xonalar hashami. Bu termin tarjima lug'atlarda "hasham, dabdaba" kabi ma'nolarni ifodalashi qayd etiladi, biroq turizm sohasida ingliz tilidagi shakli kabi qo'llanadi.

Flotel - maxsus qulayliklarga ega bo'lgan kayuta-nomerlari, faol dam olish xizmati, muzokara olib borish, konferensiya, kongress zallari, aloqa vositalari, turli barlar va restoranlardan tarkib topgan suzib yuruvchi mehmonxona.

Rotel - bir yoki ikki o'rinli vagonlardan iborat, kechki dam olishga mo'ljallangan ko'chma mehmonxona.

Though there are not such two tips of hotel (flotel and rotel) in Uzbekistan, there were recorded in touristic dictionaries. Furthermore, these structurally-simple terms were come to Uzbek directly: animatsiya, visa, vaucher, bungalo, blok, klass, reys, parking, kruiz, pansion, bar, restoran, jakuzi, kayoning, parking, port, kafeteriy, kurort, kottej, motsion, oferta, otel, palatka, piknik, plyaj, rafting, villa, dayving, safari.

Moreover, following terms are the words directly accepted to the Uzbek language: animatsiya, visa, vaucher, bungalo, blok, klass, reys, parking, kruiz, pansion, bar, restoran, jakuzi, kayoning, parking, port, kafeteriy, kurort, kottej, motsion, oferta, otel, palatka, piknik, plyaj, rafting, villa, dayving, safari and so on.

It is known that compound words in the language are born out of a certain need. Because it is not always possible to describe their specific or whole

characteristics of the objects, events and phenomena in one word (independent meaning, single root word). That's why, there is a need to express a certain concept in a new holistic word formed from the combination of two or more words.

Today emerging compound phrases in various sectors in science and technology serve for single target - to express a concept in one word. As Vinokur G.O stated: "Compound words are necessary not only to meet the needs of new words but also, indeed, to express two conception with one word." Most of the previously used compound words made up of vocabulary base, partially, Arabic and Persian words absorbed by Uzbek. In the following years, as a result of Russian and English on Uzbek new tips and models of compound words became appeared. Those, basically, were composite terms to express new notions. Compound terms components vary on according to genetic material.

The components of compound terms existent in Uzbek belong to various languages. The following tips may be:

1. Aero, avia, avto term element + compound terms: aerobika, aerodrom, aerofobiya, aeroplan, aeroport; aviabilet, aviakompaniya, avialiniya, aviatarif; avtokemping, avtoralli, avtovokzal.

2. Compound terms expressing tourism types: avtoturizm, agroturizm, mekoturizm, enoturizm, geyturizm, fotosafari.

3. Terms describing the types of healing tourism: heliotherapy (sun treatment), galotherapy (artificially created saline treatment in the microclimate of caves), hippotherapy (treatment on horseback), lithotherapy (treatment using a kamen), cryotherapy (treatment using ice or low temperatures), thalassotherapy (treatment

using the properties of seawater and its mud).

4. Composite words formed by adding "tour": tour agent, tour broker, tour document, tour leader, tour operator. The term "tour" is considered as the most active unit in usage in Tourism. The definition of it as follows: "Tour is a certain direction package of touristic services includes accommodation, catering, transport, recreation, excursion and other services .

5. Compound terms denoting the subject and objects of ecotourism: eco-resource, eco-safari, eco-tourist. Thus, compound touristic terms in Uzbek are of international character, their peculiarities are both formed by borrowing components. Terms are required to be clear and concise in each language. Moreover, it can be positive phenomenon when there is coexistence of terms systems not to reject each other. When the components of Uzbek touristic terms researched, most of them are found as compounds. The main causes of it are as followings:

1. As a matter of fact that there are not equivalents of many terms in Uzbek there have been necessity to use two and more lexical units to provide their clarity and precision.

2. Terms came to Russian from Western Europe and then introduced to Uzbek full or partial calque.

We can observe that a number of compound terms consists of two or more components, thus there are also many three-component terms in Uzbek. For example, classification of hotels made up of three components: bir yulduzli, mehmonxona, ikki yulduzli mehmonxona,

uch yulduzli mehmonxona, to'rt yulduzli mehmonxona, besh yulduzli mehmonxona.

As in Russian and English, there are dominant terms in Uzbek touristic terminology. They are "turistik", "turizm", "tur", "nomer", "klass". These terms make great part of touristic components: turistik baza, turistik bozor, turistik faoliyat, turistik faoliyat subyektlari, turistik guruh rahbari, turistik idish, turistik industriya, turistik klass, turistik klass mehmonxonasi, turistik kompleks, turistik mahsulot, mahsulot buyurtmachisi, turistik mahsulot faoliyati, turistik mahsulotni tashkillashtirish, turistik mahsulotning siljishi, turistik markaz, turistik marshrut, turistik oqim, turistik paket, turistik qiziqish, turistik yig'im and so on.

The existence many of touristic terms necessitates tourism component terms: bolalar turizmi, ekstremal turizm, gastronomik turizm, harbiy turizm, havaskorlik turizmi, ichki turizm, ijtimoiy turizm, individual turizm, karvon turizmi, kongress turizmi, madaniy turizm, milliy turizm, muzey turizmi, nikoh turizmi, reklama turizmi, sanoat turizmi, sarguzashtli turizm, sog'lomlashtirish turizmi, tog' turizmim, kichik turizm zonalari and etc.

Lexical units came out of terms "tour", "number", "class", primarily, considered as terms are in active usage in touristic service: tur militsiyasi, tur paket, tur tashkilotchisi, tur yo'llanma; bir o'rinli nomer, ikki o'rinli nomer, lyuks nomer, balkonli nomer, president nomer, uch o'rinli nomer, to'rt o'rinli nomer; turistik klass, birinchi klass, o'rta birinchi klass, o'rta turistik klass, ikkinchi klass, klassik turistik yo'nalish, yuqori sifatli birinchi klass, yuqori sifatli turistik klass.

Conclusion

It is claimed in the study that , Uzbek terminology of international tourism in general is characterized by a surplus of means of formal expression of concepts, that is, these terminologies tend to be synonymous. Touristic terms differentiate from other terminological systems with the peculiarities of fast enrichment and clear character. In world terminology there have

been conducted comparative scientific analysis in Tourism terminology testified the regulation of terms in tourism sphere and, partly, having basic tendencies to name new upcoming concepts in Tourism. Applied recommendation is one of the important tasks to regulate the terms, to choose them, to put them into practice in front of the sphere in Uzbek language.

References:

1. Mirzayev M., Aliyeva M. Turizm asoslari. – Toshkent, 2011. - B.22
2. Sirojiddinov Sh. On the factors of word acquisition // Uzbek language and literature, 2017. - № 4. - P.83.
3. Гринев-Гриневиц С.В Терминоведение, Учебное пособие. — М.: Академия, 2008. Ст – 102-104
4. Зорин И.В., Каверина Т.П., Квартальнов В.А. и др. Менеджмент туризма. Туризм как вид деятельности: Учебник. М.: Финансы и статистика, 2006. С. 406